

TAILORABLE CERAMIC CONTENT ALUMINIUM-MATRIX COMPOSITES BY SPONTANEOUS INFILTRATION

M. Pavese¹, X. Chen¹, C. Badini¹, S. Biamino¹, P. Fino¹

¹Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino
corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129, Torino, Italy
Email: matteo.pavese@polito.it, web page: <http://www.polito.it>

Keywords: Composite plates, Modal analysis, Identification, Properties, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

Since any industrial application of metal matrix composites requires low cost processes, many complex techniques for obtaining high ceramic-content composites are difficult to bring to a commercial exploitation. Spontaneous infiltration, instead, is a potentially powerful technique, if not for the complex conditions that it generally requires. In this work, a technique is described that is potentially able to guarantee spontaneous infiltration in many systems, since it depends neither on the alloy nor on a specific preform composition. Instead, the principle is based on the mixing of powders of the infiltrating metal with the ceramic, so to improve the local wetting of the preform. In this work we present the theoretical background of this model, derived from the simple Wenzel and Cassie equations, and we validate it for the Al-TiB₂-SiO₂ system by infiltration experiments. The characterization of the obtained composites is also shown, demonstrating good mechanical properties, in particular for TiB₂-rich samples, and the possibility to obtain values of stiffness and thermal expansion in a wide range, depending on the specific composition of the chosen preform.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites has been developed over decades and gradually formed an important part in materials system. Nowadays in the popularization of metal matrix composites, in emphasis for composite materials is changing from a performance-driven to a cost-driven environment. Therefore it's necessary and important to develop economical efficient techniques for producing metal matrix composites.

Spontaneous infiltration (also called pressureless infiltration) is one of the most cost efficient liquid state techniques for manufacturing high ceramic fraction metal matrix composites. It uses adhesion forces between the matrix melt and the solid preform to realize the infiltration of the metal into a porous preform. However there are several shortcomings in the existing approaches of spontaneous infiltration. For example, low infiltration rate, undesired contamination and poor mechanical properties of the initial product etc. [1-3].

In this paper a spontaneous infiltration technique for fabricating particulate reinforced aluminium matrix composites is presented. The research was focused on the problems related with both thermodynamics and kinetics of this approach. Different ceramic particulates, of different size and composition, were selected as the starting materials.

In particular, it was observed that an essential element for obtaining spontaneous infiltration was the mixing of Al powder into ceramic particulates. Al powder is believed to improve the wettability of ceramics by reacting or communicating with them ahead of the infiltration. Infiltration temperature and cold pressing pressure of the preform were found to have influence on the infiltration. During the infiltration, external melt did not fill all the pores along the infiltration path but preferentially infiltrated part of the pores throughout the preform in the beginning and then gradually spread to the rest of the pores.

In this work are presented results on the properties of aluminium matrix composites obtained from TiB₂-SiO₂-Al preforms, fabricated by spontaneous infiltration at 900 °C for 1 hour. Both TiB₂ and the Al₂O₃ formed during the infiltration had a positive influence on properties such as elastic modulus and CTE. The flexural strength instead increased with TiB₂ fraction but decreased with Al₂O₃ fraction.

Fracture analysis shows TiB₂ particles have a good bonding with the matrix while Al₂O₃ particles have a poor one.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

TiB₂-Al₂O₃-Al composites were fabricated by a reactive spontaneous infiltration technology. The processing steps comprise: TiB₂- SiO₂-Al mixture preparation, preform forming, sealing into Al alloy moulds and pressureless infiltration. TiB₂ powders (2.5-3.5 μm, from ABCR), SiO₂ powders (-400 mesh, Alfa Aesar) and Al powders (-325 mesh, from Alfa Aesar) were used as starting materials. 6060 aluminium alloy (from CO.ME.F.I. Metalli srl) was used to prepare the moulds for sealing, and served also as infiltration bath after melting.

The procedure of fabricating the composites comprises blending the ceramic powders with aluminium powders in ethanol for 2 hours, filtering out the solvent and drying the powders mixtures at 80 °C for 2 hours, cold-pressing the powders mixtures into a green preform in a 6060-alloy mould, sealing the alloy mould and heating the sealed mould to 900 °C for 1 h and air-cooling the composites after infiltration.

The main alloying elements of 6060 alloy are Si (0.3-0.6 wt.%) and Mg (0.35-0.6 wt.%). In Table 1 the main properties of the 6060 alloys are reported.

Property		annealed	T4 state	T6 state
Yield strength	[MPa]	40	120	230
Ultimate strength	[MPa]	80	170	230
Elongation at fracture	[%]	20	22	12
Young's modulus	[GPa]	66		
CTE	[10 ⁻⁶ /K]	23.6		

Table 1: properties of the 6060 Al alloy.

3 WETTABILITY ANALYSIS OF INFILTRATION

To consider the spontaneous infiltration phenomenon in a thermodynamic manner, Young equation is no more sufficient because the surface involved are no longer smooth and chemically homogeneous.

For a rough homogeneous surface, Wenzel [4-5] developed the following equation:

$$\cos \theta_Y^W = r \cos \theta_Y \quad (1)$$

where θ_Y is the contact angle given by Young equation, r is the roughness factor equals to the ratio of surface area to the projected area of the surface.

For a heterogeneous smooth surface, Cassie [6-7] gave the equation for the equilibrium contact angle as:

$$\cos \theta_Y^C = f^A \cos \theta_Y^A + f^B \cos \theta_Y^B \quad (2)$$

where f^i refers to the area fraction of the component surface.

The critical condition for a spontaneous infiltration is that the overall contact angle should be smaller than 90°. The determination of overall contact angle can refer to Wenzel and Cassie equations. In the infiltration experiments, a sufficient aluminium addition in the green preform was found an essential condition for the spontaneous infiltration. This confirmed a poor wetting of the ceramics by aluminium, but also suggested that the aluminium addition brought to the formation of phases that were well wetted by aluminium. When sufficient aluminium was added the equilibrium contact angle was moved from over 90° to less than 90° according to Cassie equation.

A simple hypothesis for the explanation of this phenomenon is described here. The phase that wets well is aluminium itself. Aluminium can be believed to be perfectly wetted by aluminium, while the various types of ceramics present differences in chemical composition that bring different contact angles and thus different amount of aluminium content required for a spontaneous infiltration. The effect of size of the particles must also be considered. Since a larger particle size results in smaller

surface area with the same volume, less aluminium addition is required in big-sized ceramics with respect to small-sized ones. Regarding temperature, generally at high temperature the contact angle of the ceramics is lower than at a low temperature, as a result the critical amount of aluminium addition for a spontaneous infiltration decreases with temperature. Also the observed cold pressing pressure dependence can be explained: under a high pressure the additional aluminium particulates are deformed plastically, in other words the gaps between the ceramic particulates restricting the aluminium particles are more narrow which results in higher surface area of primary aluminium phase even when aluminium is melt, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: behaviour of particulate under pressure.

Based on these assumption a simple model was built for the wetting behaviour, according to Cassie and Wenzel equations.

$$\cos \theta = f_{Ceramic} r_{Ceramic} \cos \theta_{Ceramic} + f_{Al} r_{Al} \cos \theta_{Al} \quad (3)$$

where f^i refers to the area fraction of the component surface. From this equation, through simple passages, we can calculate the following:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{\frac{y_{Ceramic}}{R_{Ceramic}}}{\frac{y_{Ceramic}}{R_{Ceramic}} + (1+k(p))\frac{y_{Al}}{R_{Al}}} r_{Ceramic} \cos \theta_{Ceramic} + \frac{(1+k(p))\frac{y_{Al}}{R_{Al}}}{\frac{y_{Ceramic}}{R_{Ceramic}} + (1+k(p))\frac{y_{Al}}{R_{Al}}} r_{Al} \cos \theta_{Al} \quad (4)$$

where y is the volume ratio of the components of the mixture, R is the powder size, $k(p)$ is a factor concerning the deformation of the Al particles during cold pressing.

Another matter must be however kept in consideration: in Cassie equation the solubility of the solid phases in the liquid ones is not considered. This refers to the fact that Al powders melt and mix with the Al of the bath. So the previous model must be modified, and can be adjusted by using the contact angle hysteresis concept [8]. By using the concepts of advancing and receding angles, the following expression was derived:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{V_{pore}}{V_{pore} + V_{Al}} \cos \theta_A + \frac{V_{Al}}{V_{pore} + V_{Al}} \cos \theta_R \quad (5)$$

where V_{pore} and V_{Al} refer to the relative volume of pores and Al powders in the preform.

By using equations (4) and (5) the influence of ceramic properties, powder size, temperature, and cold pressing pressure could be well explained. Firstly, the chemical differences in the ceramic powders gave different advancing and receding contact angles, bringing to different critical amount of aluminium addition for spontaneous infiltration. Secondly, the larger the difference in particle size between ceramic and Al, the lower the porosity, which results in better wetting. Third, the temperature decreases both advancing and receding contact angle and improves the wetting. Finally, the cold pressing pressure improves wetting by reducing the porosity.

To check the model, three-components series were designed, spontaneously infiltrated and investigated. In this case the Al-TiB₂-SiO₂ is shown. A triangle is used to describe the composition,

like in 3-components phase diagrams.

With three components, the equations becomes more complicated, Equation (4) becomes:

$$\cos_{\theta} = \frac{(1+k(p)) \frac{1}{R_{Al}} r_{Al} \cos_{\theta_{Al}}}{\frac{y_C^1}{R_C^1} + \frac{y_C^2}{R_C^2} + (1+k(p)) \frac{y_{Al}}{R_{Al}}} \left(y_C^1 \frac{y_{Al}^1}{y_{Al}^1 - 1} + y_C^2 \frac{y_{Al}^2}{y_{Al}^2 - 1} + y_{Al} \right) \quad (6)$$

where the ¹ and ² apices refers to the two ceramics. Thus, the condition for spontaneous infiltration limits to:

$$y_C^1 \frac{y_{Al}^1}{y_{Al}^1 - 1} + y_C^2 \frac{y_{Al}^2}{y_{Al}^2 - 1} + y_{Al} \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

The condition relative to equation (5) instead is transformed into the:

$$\cos_{\theta} = \frac{1}{\frac{y_C^1}{R_C^1} + \frac{y_C^2}{R_C^2} \frac{P}{1-P} + y_{Al}} \left[\left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^1}{P^1} y_{Al}^1 \right) \frac{y_C^1}{R_C^1} \cos_{\theta_{R^1}} + \left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^2}{P^2} y_{Al}^2 \right) \frac{y_C^2}{R_C^2} \cos_{\theta_{R^2}} \right] \quad (8)$$

where P is the porosity. The condition for spontaneous infiltration is, this time:

$$\left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^1}{P^1} y_{Al}^1 \right) y_C^1 + \frac{R_C^1 \cos_{\theta_{R^2}}}{R_C^2 \cos_{\theta_{R^1}}} \left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^2}{P^2} y_{Al}^2 \right) y_C^2 \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

To solve this inequality, the relationship between porosity and volume ratio is required. Thus, the two coefficients

$$f_1 = \left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^1}{P^1} y_{Al}^1 \right) y_C^1 \quad \text{and} \quad f_2 = \left(y_{Al} - \frac{P}{1-P} \frac{1-P^2}{P^2} y_{Al}^2 \right) y_C^2 \quad (10)$$

are obtained, and a positive coefficient k is defined.

$$k = \frac{R_C^1 \cos_{\theta_{R^2}}}{R_C^2 \cos_{\theta_{R^1}}} \quad (11)$$

If both f functions are negative, the inequality (9) cannot be satisfied, so that this defines an area of impossible infiltration. If both f functions are positive, the spontaneous infiltration occurs, if only one of the f functions is positive, the k value is needed to verify if spontaneous infiltration will take place or not. In Fig. 2a these three areas are defined for the Al-TiB₂-SiO₂ case.

Figure 2: (a) the infiltrated area (sky blue), non-infiltrated area (violet), possibly infiltrated area (ochre). (b) the effect of coefficient k value on the infiltration zone boundary

On Fig. 2b it is evident how a smaller k coefficient guarantees a wider infiltration zone. This coefficient depends on the ratio between the sizes of the two powders and on the receding contact angle of aluminium on the two ceramics, which is hard to obtain. Thus it was evaluated experimentally, from infiltration maps, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: (a) infiltration map of the Al-TiB₂-SiO₂ system. (b) the interpolation of the infiltration boundary with k values.

In this case the k coefficient is close to 0.1, which is a reasonable number since SiO₂ powder was way larger in size than TiB₂ one and since the contact angle of aluminium with TiB₂ is smaller than with SiO₂.

4 CHARACTERIZATION OF INFILTRATED COMPOSITES

For a correct analysis of the infiltrated composites, it must be remembered that when Al melts, the reaction

takes place. This reaction brings to the formation of aluminium oxide from the starting silica, while the formed silicon dissolves in the aluminium matrix. Thus the results are shown here as a function of TiB₂ or Al₂O₃ content, not anymore on SiO₂, which was instead necessary to cope with the infiltration mechanism.

In Fig. 4a it is shown the effect of the content of TiB₂ on elastic modulus, while the effect of Al₂O₃ content is shown in Fig. 4b.

Figure 4: elastic modulus of composites as a function of (a) the TiB₂ content (b) the Al₂O₃ content.

In Fig. 5a and 5b the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) is presented for the same samples.

Figure 5: thermal expansion coefficient of composites as a function of (a) the TiB_2 content (b) the Al_2O_3 content.

Finally, in Fig. 6a and 6b the flexural resistance is presented for the same samples.

Figure 6: flexural strength of composites as a function of (a) the TiB_2 content (b) the Al_2O_3 content.

From the analysis of Fig. 4, 5 and 6, it is possible to make several considerations. First, the TiB_2 content, i.e. the content of the wetting phase, influences almost linearly the stiffness, thermal expansion, and has the most marked influence on strength. The Al_2O_3 content instead, i.e. the content of the non-wetting phase, influences only minimally the properties. If a sufficient TiB_2 quantity is present, the elastic modulus slightly improves with the Al_2O_3 content, but when no TiB_2 is present, the increased quantity of alumina causes a small reduction of stiffness. Regarding CTE, the Al_2O_3 content has a similar effect than TiB_2 , i.e. causes a reduction of thermal expansion, albeit not linear. With flexural strength, instead, the Al_2O_3 increases causes almost always a reduction of strength.

The reason for this phenomenon is probably to be sought in the good or bad quality of the interface between the alloy and the ceramic. Two images of the fracture surface of an Al-TiB_2 sample (Fig. 7a) and an $\text{Al-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample (Fig. 7b) show very different fracture surfaces.

Figure 7: fracture surface of a (a) Al-TiB₂ composite (b) Al-Al₂O₃ composite.

The Al-TiB₂ interface is good, and the fracture surface shows an extensive plastic deformation. The Al-Al₂O₃ fracture surface instead has many voids, low plastic deformation and seems governed by porosity. That the Al-Al₂O₃ wetting angle is poor is known, but a good interface is observed for instance in the Al-Al₂O₃ samples obtained by reactive metal penetration [9], while in this case the interface seems rather poor.

Overall, the characterization shown in Fig. 4, 5, 6 shows that the samples present a wide range of stiffness, CTE and flexural strength values, showing that the infiltration technique presented in this work can provide a wide combination of properties, suggesting that this technique allows to produce materials with properties determined by the design of the material and not vice versa.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work a technique for obtaining spontaneous infiltration of mixture of ceramic powders was studied both from the theoretical and experimental point of view. By a simple analysis of wettability issues a model was built that allows to explain the infiltration behaviour of ceramic preforms in the Al-TiB₂-SiO₂ system. The properties of the prepared composites show depends significantly on the ceramic content, but the influence of the wetting ceramic, TiB₂, is much higher than the influence of the non-wetting one, SiO₂. In any case, by conveniently choosing the composition of the system, it is possible to partially tailor the properties of the composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author Xiang Chen (2010612033) would like to acknowledge the Chinese Scholarship council (CSC) for financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] B.S.S. Daniel, V.S.R. Murthy, Directed melt oxidation and nitridation of aluminium alloys: a comparison, *Materials & Design*, **16**, 1995, pp. 155-161 (doi: 10.1016/0261-3069(95)00035-6)
- [2] H. Venugopalan, T. DebRoy, Growth stage kinetics in the synthesis of Al₂O₃/Al composites by directed oxidation of Al-Mg and Al-Mg-Si alloys, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, **16**, 1996, pp. 1351-1363 (doi: 10.1016/0955-2219(96)00068-4)
- [3] Q. Zhang, X. Ma, G. Wu, Interfacial microstructure of SiCp/Al composite produced by the pressureless infiltration technique, *Ceramics International*, **39**, 2013, pp. 4893-4897 (doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.11.082)
- [4] R.N. Wenzel, Resistance of solid surfaces to wetting by water, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry*, **28**, 1936, pp. 988-994 (doi: 10.1021/ie50320a024)
- [5] R.N. Wenzel, Surface Roughness and Contact Angle, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, **53**, 1949, pp. 1466-1467 (doi: 10.1021/j150474a015)
- [6] P.S. Swain, R. Lipowsky, Contact angles on heterogeneous surfaces: A new look at Cassie's and Wenzel's laws, *Langmuir*, **14**, 1998, pp. 6772-6780 (doi: 10.1021/la980602k)

- [7] A. Cassie, Contact angles, *Discussions of the Faraday Society*, **3**, 1948, pp. 11-16 (doi: 10.1039/df9480300011)
- [8] H.B. Eral, D.J.C.M. 't Mannetje, J.M. Oh, Contact angle hysteresis: a review of fundamentals and applications, *Colloid and Polymer Science*, **291**, 2013, pp. 247-260 (doi: 10.1007/s00396-012-2796-6)
- [9] M. Pavese, P. Fino, D. Ugues, C. Badini, high cycle fatigue study of metal-ceramic co-continuous composites, *Scripta Materialia*, **55**, 2006, pp. 1135-1138 (doi: 10.1016/j.scriptamat.2006.08.025)